

ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF 3D ADDING RIBS RE-ENTRANT CELLULAR STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, elastic properties of 3D augmented re-entrant cellular structure are proposed based on the 3D re-entrant cellular structure and the 2D augmented re-entrant honeycomb. Analytical and finite element (FE) simulations are carried out to calculate the elastic properties of the 3D new design. Opposite to 2D situation, Poisson's ratio of the proposed 3D design has a negative value in one direction for all force constant of the adding struts. Similar to 2D structure, the 3D new structure has a great enhancement on the Young's modulus. For its significant Young's modulus enhancement and negative Poisson's ratio in one direction for all topology and adding struts' force constant, this layout can be considered as a possible basis to design new concepts of structures with negative Poisson's ratio in one direction and zero or positive Poisson's ratio in other two directions. We also show the main mechanism of the enhancement of the adding ribs re-entrant structure for the first time.

1 INTRODUCTION

Auxetic materials, show lateral shrinkage upon axial compression, exhibit negative Poisson's ratios. Due to their unique mechanical properties usage of auxetic materials can be in aerospace applications, the biomedical area, sensors, and could potentially be used for completely new structures with special functions [1]. Re-entrant structure is one of the classical auxetic structures. Many researchers have report the investigation on the 2D re-entrant structures [2,3]. However, simple 2D approximations fail to model the properties of the 3D network accurately and a full 3D analysis is required. By modeling the 3D unit cell as idealized 14-sided unit cell, Choi and Lakes [4] gave the Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios of conventional and re-entrant open cell foams. However, studies on 3D auxetic structures are limited due to the lack of manufacturing methods in realizing many of the complex designs. In recent, with the development of manufacturing of cellular structures, it becomes possible to utilize analytical modeling methods to accurately design for the performance of an auxetic cellular structure [5-8]. Simultaneously, analytical methods are carried out to calculate properties of 3D re-entrant auxetic structures also. Based on a large deflection beam model and a Timoshenko beam model, Yang et al. gave an analytical solution for the Young's modulus, Poisson's ratios and yield strength of a 3D re-entrant auxetic cellular structure [9]. By comparing with experimentation and finite element analysis, they verified their analytical model to be a convenient and relatively accurate method in the prediction of the performance for the auxetic cellular structures [9].

Auxetic materials are widely used in fields of aerospace, biomedical, sensors, and could be used for new structures with special functions, due to its unique properties. However, structural applications of auxetic materials are limited due to its low stiff value [10]. Re-entrant honeycomb were modified for structural applications [11]. What is more, an 2D adding ribs re-entrant honeycomb with enhanced Young's modulus, negative Poisson's ratio, and retention most spaces of the re-entrant honeycomb was proposed by the author previously [12].

In this paper, a 3D adding ribs re-entrant auxetic structure is proposed to improve the mechanical properties of 3D re-entrant auxetic structures. This structure exhibits orthotropic mechanical properties and could be readily patterned into 3D geometries. Analytical and FE simulations are carried out in all three principal directions in detail to calculate the Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus of the new configuration under uniaxial loading. It is shown that some properties of the proposed 3D new design

are similar with 2D situation, however, some other are not. Main mechanism of the enhancement, effect length of the struts, limitation of the enhancement, and the negative Poisson's ratio in one direction for all topology of the 3D new design are given in the discussions.

2. ANALYTICAL MODEL

Inspired by the 3D re-entrant auxetic cellular structure (see Fig. 1a) and the 2D adding ribs re-entrant honeycomb (see Fig. 1c), we give a 3D adding ribs re-entrant cellular structure (see Fig. 2). Without losing generality, it was assumed in the modeling that the cross sectional shape of the struts in the 3D adding ribs cellular structure is square. There are four primary design parameters for the unit cell structure: the length of the struts h , the length of the re-entrant struts l , the re-entrant angle θ , and the thickness of the strut cross section t (see Fig. 1c). Note that the strut cross sectional dimension is not shown in Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1. (a) Unit cell of 3D re-entrant cellular auxetic structure [33] (b) geometrical of 3D re-entrant auxetic cellular structure and [9] (c) geometry and coordinate system of 2D adding ribs re-entrant honeycomb [12].

2.1 Force Constant

Fig. 2. Force analysis of the unit cell of 3D new design (loading in direction 2; the yellow ones are the adding struts).

From the geometry of the unit cell shown in Fig. 2, the symmetry of the unit cell dictates that the mechanical properties along the 2 and 3 directions are identical. Therefore, only the elastic properties

in two directions (1 and either 2 or 3) need to be analyzed to fully describe the structure's behavior. From the representative volume element of the 3D new design (see Fig. 2), it is clear that the unit cell of the new design can be divided into two parts: the re-entrant part (Fig. 2 in green part) and the adding ribs part (Fig. 2 in yellow part).

In this paper we use the force constant model [13] to give the elastic properties of the 3D adding ribs model. The force constants relate the displacement of the struts of a cellular structure to the applied force which causes it. For all three mechanisms (flexing, hinging and stretching), the force constant K_i is defined by the general relationship [13]

$$F = K_i \delta_i, \quad (1)$$

where F is the applied force, K_i is the force constant, and δ_i is the displacement. For re-entrant cells shown in Fig. 1, force constant is given by [13]

$$K_f^l = E_s b t^3 / l^3, \quad (2a)$$

$$K_s^l = E_s b t / l, \quad (2b)$$

$$K_h^h = E_s b t / h, \quad (2c)$$

$$K_h^l = G_s b t / l, \quad (2d)$$

where K_f^l , K_s^l , and K_h^l are the flexing, stretching, and hinging force constants of the strut l respectively. K_s^h is the stretching force constant of strut h . The intrinsic Young's modulus and shear modulus of the material forming the re-entrant part are E_s and G_s respectively.

The adding ribs stretching force constant $K_s^{h_0}$ is an important parameter. Compared with Eq. (2), the stretching force constant of the adding ribs h_0 is

$$K_s^{h_0} = E_s' b t / h_0, \quad (3)$$

where h_0 is the length of the adding ribs, E_s' is the adding ribs' intrinsic Young's modulus. In order to simplify the analytical and FE simulation, the force constant $K_s^{h_0}$ is changing by change of the adding ribs' intrinsic Young's modulus E_s' and both the adding struts h_0 and the the original struts h have an cross section thickness t . From the deformation of the proposed 3D structure, stretching of the adding ribs and the flexing of the inclined struts must be considered in the model.

2.2 Loading Along Direction 2

Consider the unit cell subjected to a tensile load $4F$ in direction 2 (Fig. 2). Due to the symmetry of the structure, force analysis and deformation of the unit cell when loading in direction 2 is shown in Fig. 3. It should be noticing that the deformation of the inclined struts in direction 2 and 3 are different due to the total force of the unit cell in direction 2 is $4F$ while the total force in direction 3 is zero.

Fig. 3. Force analysis of the unit cell in (a) 12 plane and (b) 13 plane; deformation of the unit cell in (c) 12 plane and (d) 13 plane (loading in direction 2).

In direction 2, the force applied on point B must equal to F , i. e.

$$F_t^2 \cos \theta + F_n^2 \sin \theta = F \quad (4)$$

The resultant force applied on point A in direction 1 must be zero, then we have

$$F_1 - F_2 - 2F_n^2 \cos \theta + 2F_t^2 \sin \theta - 2F_n^3 \cos \theta - 2F_t^3 \sin \theta = 0 \quad (5)$$

In direction 1, the structure is assumed to deform freely, then the total force must be zero, i.e.

$$F_1 + F_2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

While in direction 3, the structure is assumed to deform freely, then the total force must be zero, i.e.

$$F_n^3 \sin \theta - F_t^3 \cos \theta = 0 \quad (7)$$

Considering deformation compatibility condition of 12 plane (Fig. 3c), we have

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F_2}{K_s^{h_0}} - \frac{F_1}{K_s^h} \right) = \frac{F_n^2}{K_f^l} \cos \theta - \frac{F_t^2}{K_s^l} \sin \theta \quad (8)$$

The deformation compatibility condition of 13 plane (Fig. 3d) gives

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{F_2}{K_s^{h_0}} - \frac{F_1}{K_s^h} \right) = \frac{F_n^3}{K_f^l} \cos \theta + \frac{F_t^3}{K_s^l} \sin \theta \quad (9)$$

Solving the coupled Eqs. (4), (5), (6), (7), (8), and (9), we have

$$F_1 = F \frac{1/K_s^l - \varphi}{\varphi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \tan \theta \quad (10a)$$

$$F_2 = F \frac{\varphi - 1/K_s^l}{\varphi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \tan \theta \quad (10b)$$

$$F_n^2 = F \left(\frac{\varphi - 1/K_s^l}{\varphi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{2\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi K_s^l} \right) \sin \theta \quad (10c)$$

$$F_t^2 = F \left(\frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} - \frac{\phi - 1/K_s^l}{\phi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{2\phi} - \frac{1}{\phi K_s^l} \right) \tan \theta \sin \theta \quad (10d)$$

$$F_n^3 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\phi - 1/K_s^l}{\phi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{\phi} \sin \theta \quad (10e)$$

$$F_t^3 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\phi - 1/K_s^l}{\phi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{\phi} \tan \theta \sin \theta \quad (10f)$$

where,

$$\phi = \cos^2 \theta / K_f^l + \sin^2 \theta / K_s^l \quad (11)$$

Then, by calculate the displacement in each directions, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio in direction 2 could be obtained as

$$E_2 = \frac{2}{(h + h_0)} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{K_s^l} + \left(\frac{\phi - 1/K_s^l}{\phi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{2\phi} + \frac{1}{\phi K_s^l} \right) \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin^2 \theta} \quad (12)$$

$$v_{21} = -\frac{l}{h + h_0} \frac{\frac{(\phi - 1/K_s^l)(K_s^h - K_s^{h_0})}{\phi K_s^{h_0} K_s^h + K_s^{h_0} + K_s^h}}{\frac{1}{K_s^l} + \left(\frac{\phi - 1/K_s^l}{\phi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{2\phi} + \frac{1}{\phi K_s^l} \right) \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin^2 \theta} \quad (13)$$

$$v_{23} = -\frac{\left(\frac{\phi - 1/K_s^l}{\phi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{2\phi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin^2 \theta}{\frac{1}{K_s^l} + \left(\frac{\phi - 1/K_s^l}{\phi + 1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h} \frac{1/K_s^{h_0} + 1/K_s^h}{2\phi} + \frac{1}{\phi K_s^l} \right) \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin^2 \theta} \quad (14)$$

Due to the symmetry of the 3D cellular structure the Young's modulus in direction 3 E_3 equals to E_2 , the Poisson's ratio v_{31} equals to v_{21} , v_{32} equals to v_{23} .

2.3 Loading Along Direction 1

Similar with the situation when loading along direction 2, the Young's modulus in direction 1 is given by

$$E_1 = \frac{\sigma_1}{\varepsilon_1} = \frac{h_0 + h}{l^2 \cos^2 \theta} \frac{\phi K_s^{h_0} K_s^h + K_s^{h_0} + K_s^h}{\phi K_s^{h_0} + \phi K_s^h + 4} \quad (15)$$

While the Poisson's ratio v_{12} could be given as

$$v_{12} = -\frac{\varepsilon_2}{\varepsilon_1} = -\frac{h_0 + h}{2l} \frac{K_s^h - K_s^{h_0}}{\phi K_s^h + \phi K_s^{h_0} + 4} \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin \theta \quad (16)$$

Due to the symmetry of the unit cell, v_{13} equals to v_{12} .

2.4 A General Model

A general expression for Young's modulus as well as Poisson's ratio should combine all three mechanisms of flexing, hinging, and stretching together. From Timoshenko beam theory, the displacement of the re-entrant strut l corresponding to the hinging mechanisms could be expressed as [13]

$$\delta_h = \gamma l \quad (17)$$

where γ is the shear strain, which in turn have the following relationships:

$$\gamma = F_n / \kappa G_s A \quad (18)$$

where, κ is the geometrical factor, F_n is the vertical force on the re-entrant strut and A is the cross sectional area of the strut. From Eq. (1) the hinging constant of the re-entrant strut K_h^l based on the Timoshenko beam theory could be obtained by

$$K_h^l = \kappa G_s b t / l \quad (19)$$

In the case of a rectangular cross section, $\kappa = 5/6$. Comparing this equation with Eq. (2d) it is easy to find that for small deformation, the force constant model and the Timoshenko beam theory are very similar with each other. Considering the hinging mechanism of the re-entrant struts in the deformation compatibility conditions loading in direction 1 and 2, the parameter φ changes to

$$\varphi^* = \cos^2 \theta / K_f^l + \cos^2 \theta / K_h^l + \sin^2 \theta / K_s^l \quad (20)$$

The corresponding Young's modulus E_1 , E_2 as well as Poisson's ratios ν_{12} , ν_{21} and ν_{23} could be obtained by substituting Eq. (20) into Eqs. (15), (12), (16), (13) and (14) respectively.

3. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Using a similar method given in [12], linear elastic FE models has been created to determine the elastic properties of the 3D adding ribs re-entrant structure. The ABAQUS commercial package has been used to perform these analyses. Periodic boundary conditions are considered in the FE models. The models are developed using C3D8R quadrilateral 8 nodes linear brick with reduced integration. The intrinsic Young's modulus of the re-entrant part of the unit cell is assumed to be 1000MPa, and the intrinsic Poisson's ratio is assumed to be 0.3. The intrinsic Poisson's ratio of the adding ribs is assumed to be 0.3 also. Averaging the normal forces on the loaded boundaries, the resulting homogenized stresses are calculated. Then dividing the averaged uniaxial stresses by the imposed strain, the Young's modulus is calculated. The transverse strains are obtained by averaging the transverse displacements opposite the loaded boundaries. At last, dividing the homogenized transverse strain by the uniaxial imposed ones we can obtain the Poisson's ratios.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Before discussion we define several parameters: cell struts' force constant ratio $\lambda = K_s^{h_0} / K_s^h$, cell struts aspect ratio $\alpha = h / l$, and the re-entrant struts thickness to length ratio $\beta = t / l$. What is more, elastic properties of 3D re-entrant cellular structure corresponding to the 3D structure we proposed should be given either.

4.1 Elastic Properties of 3D Re-entrant Cellular Structure

Analytical and experiment studies on 3D re-entrant cellular structure have be given by Yang et al. [14]. Young's modulus E_1 and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} of the 3D periodic re-entrant lattice is given as [14]

$$E_1 = \frac{\alpha - \sin \theta}{\frac{2\alpha^2 \cos^2 \theta}{E_s t^2} + \left(\frac{l^4}{2E_s t^4} + \frac{3l^2}{5G_s t^2} \right) \cos^4 \theta} \quad (21)$$

$$\nu_{12} = - \frac{\left(\frac{l^2}{4E_s t^4} + \frac{3}{10G_s t^2} \right) (\alpha - \sin \theta) \sin \theta}{\frac{\alpha}{E_s t^2} + \left(\frac{l^2}{4E_s t^4} + \frac{3}{10G_s t^2} \right) \cos^2 \theta} \quad (22)$$

It should be point out that this modeling analytical equations match well with the experiments, as well as the FEA results [14]. Based on a similar force constant method used in this paper and simplified

details, the Young's modulus E_2 and the Poisson's ratio ν_{21} and ν_{23} of the 3D re-entrant cellular structure could be expressed as

$$E_2 = \frac{1}{h-l \sin \theta} \frac{1}{\frac{\varphi+1/K_s^l}{2\varphi} \left(\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_f^l} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_s^l} \right) + \frac{1}{K_s^l}} \quad (23)$$

$$\nu_{21} = -\frac{l \sin \theta}{4(h-l \sin \theta)} \frac{\varphi-1/K_s^l}{\frac{\varphi+1/K_s^l}{2\varphi} \left(\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_f^l} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_s^l} \right) + \frac{1}{K_s^l}} \quad (24)$$

$$\nu_{23} = -\frac{\frac{\varphi-1/K_s^l}{2\varphi} \left(\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_f^l} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_s^l} \right)}{\frac{\varphi+1/K_s^l}{2\varphi} \left(\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_f^l} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_s^l} \right) + \frac{1}{K_s^l}} \quad (25)$$

where, φ is also given in Eq. (11).

4.2 Comparison Between 3D New Topology and 3D Re-entrant Cellular Structure

Analytical and FE comparison between 3D re-entrant cellular structure and new 3D topology carried for $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 0.05$ is shown in Figs. 6. It can be seen that the analytical results match well with the FE simulations, even with small re-entrant angles (Figs. 6). For $\beta = 0.05$ the Poisson's ratio ν_{23} increases with θ to a value around -1 and have a little decrease (Fig. 6b). Also, a good agreement between the analytical and FE simulations of the 3D new structure could be found (Figs. 6).

Fig. 6. Analytical and FE comparison between 3D re-entrant cellular structure and 3D new design (a) stiffness ratio value E / E_s and (b) Poisson's ratio ν proposed for $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 0.05$ (scatters and the line with symbols corresponding to the FE and analytical simulations respectively; analytical simulations of the 3D new design are based on the general model).

In the 2D model [12], it was shown that Young's modulus enhanced a lot while the Poisson's ratio does not reduce too much. From Fig. 6, a similar result is obtained in the 3D situation. For $\beta = 0.05$ and $\lambda = 0.01$, Poisson's ratio ν_{12} do not have an obvious reduce when θ changes. However, Poisson's ratio ν_{21} and ν_{23} have a certain reduce when θ is below 20° . Similar with the 2D re-entrant honeycomb [3,13], 2D adding ribs re-entrant honeycomb [12], and 3D re-entrant model [14], there is also a slightly decrease of Young's modulus E_1 / E_s and then increase with θ of the 3D new design (Figs. 6a).

For $\beta = 0.05$, there is a significant enhancement of stiffness value E_1 / E_s in the range of small internal angles. For an internal angle of 10° , a stiffness value E_1 / E_s variation can be seen from around 6.64×10^{-5} (259% of re-entrant model [14]) to a value of 4.54×10^{-4} (1769.8% of re-entrant model [14]) when the force constant ratio λ becomes from 0.01 to 0.1. The enhancement is not so significant for stiffness value E_2 / E_s , it is from a value around 4.44×10^{-4} (202.6% of re-entrant model) for $\lambda = 0.01$ to a value of 1.03×10^{-3} (469.9% of re-entrant model) for $\lambda = 0.1$. For the Poisson's ratio ν_{12} , a value around -0.316 (98.2% of re-entrant model [14]) for $\lambda = 0.01$ to a value of -0.226 (81.3% of re-entrant model [14]) for $\lambda = 0.1$ can be seen. For the Poisson's ratio ν_{21} , a value around -2.04 (77.1% of re-entrant model) for $\lambda = 0.01$ to a value of -0.58 (21.9% of re-entrant model) for $\lambda = 0.1$ can be found. However, for the Poisson's ratio ν_{23} , a value around -0.663 (79.4% of re-entrant model) for $\lambda = 0.01$ to a value of -0.218 (26.2% of re-entrant model) for $\lambda = 0.1$ can be seen. Increasing the internal angle to 60° , for $\lambda = 0.01$, both the stiffness value E_1 / E_s and E_2 / E_s have a 25% increase, while the Poisson's ratio, ν_{12} , ν_{21} and ν_{23} have a 2% decrease. For $\lambda = 0.1$, both the stiffness value E_1 / E_s and E_2 / E_s have an increase more than 370%, while the Poisson's ratio ν_{12} , ν_{21} and ν_{23} have a decrease less than 23%. It is worth noticing that for large internal angles, the enhancement of stiffness value E_1 / E_s and E_2 / E_s are almost equal. It should be point out that with β increase the enhancement of the stiffness value is decrease (see Figs. 6a).

Similar with the 2D situation [12], although not shown here, it could be proved that the Young's modulus E is larger than the 3D re-entrant structure, while the Poisson's ratio ν is smaller than the original one.

Fig. 7. Analytical and FE simulations of stiffness ratio value E / E_s and Poisson's ratio ν of the 3D new design carried for $\beta = 0.05$, $\theta = 30^\circ$ and $\alpha = 2$ (scatters and line with symbols corresponding to the FE and analytical simulations respectively).

4.3 Negative Poisson's Ratio ν_{23}

The force constant ratio λ is an important parameter for the 3D new structure. Analytical and FE simulations of stiffness ratio value E / E_s and Poisson's ratio ν of the 3D new design carried for (a) $\beta = 0.05$ and (b) $\beta = 0.1$ with $\theta = 30^\circ$ and $\alpha = 2$ is shown in Fig. 7. Similar with the 2D situation [12], Poisson's ratio ν_{12} and ν_{21} equals to zero when $\lambda = 1$, i. e. the force constant $K_s^{h_0}$ equals to K_s^h .

However, the Poisson's ratio ν_{23} still have a negative value when $\lambda > 1$. It can be proved that Poisson's ratio ν_{23} is negative for all $\lambda > 0$. In fact, for all $\lambda > 0$ and $t < l$, from Eq. (2a) and (2b) it is easy to find that

$$K_f^l < K_s^l. \quad (26)$$

Substituting this equation to Eq. (11) we have

$$\varphi > 1/K_s^l > 0. \quad (27)$$

Then, substituting this equation into Eqs. (10a) and (10b) we have

$$F_1 < 0, \quad (28a)$$

$$F_2 > 0, \quad (28b)$$

i. e. the strut h applied a tensile load while the strut h_0 applied a compress load. The deformation of the unit cell in 13 plane is shown in Fig. 8. Considering the symmetry of the structure, assumed the center-line do not move, the strut h is shrinkage while the strut h_0 is longer simultaneously, i.e. the unit cell is expand in direction 3 for all $\lambda > 0$ and $t < l$. For this unique property the proposed 3D structure is an excellent choice for the structures which have zero Poisson's ratios in two directions and negative Poisson's ratio in the third one.

Fig. 8. Deformation of the unit cell in 13 plane when loading along direction 2 ($F_1 < 0$, $F_2 > 0$).

4.4 Linear Relationship

In 2D situation [12], an evident linear relationship between Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio is found when λ is changing and θ , t , h , l , b are constants. For the 3D cellular structure we proposed here, similar relationship could be found. Analytical and FE simulations of Poisson's ratio ν as a function of Young's modulus E/E_s of the 3D new design carried for $\alpha = 2$, $\beta = 0.1$ and $\theta = 30^\circ$ is shown in Fig. 9. An evident linear relationship between Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio could be found both for the Analytical and FE simulations. In fact, as we have

$$K_s^{h_0} = \lambda K_s^h \quad (29)$$

Substituting this equation into Eqs. (12), (13), (14), (15) and (16) we have

$$E_1 = \frac{\sigma_1}{\varepsilon_1} = \frac{h_0 + h}{l^2 \cos^2 \theta} \frac{\varphi \lambda K_s^h K_s^h + \lambda K_s^h + K_s^h}{\varphi \lambda K_s^h + \varphi K_s^h + 4} \quad (30)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{2}{(h + h_0)} \frac{\lambda(\varphi K_s^h + 1)K_s^l + K_s^l}{\lambda c_0 + c_1} \quad (31)$$

$$\nu_{12} = -\frac{\varepsilon_2}{\varepsilon_1} = -\frac{h_0 + h}{2l} \frac{K_s^h - \lambda K_s^h}{\varphi K_s^h + \varphi \lambda K_s^h + 4} \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin \theta \quad (32)$$

$$v_{21} = \frac{l \sin \theta}{(h+h_0)} \frac{\lambda(\varphi K_s^l - 1) - \varphi K_s^l + 1}{\lambda c_0 + c_1} \quad (33)$$

$$v_{23} = - \frac{(\lambda+1) \frac{\varphi K_s^l - 1}{2\varphi} \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin^2 \theta}{\lambda c_0 + c_1} \quad (34)$$

where,

$$c_0 = \left(\frac{\varphi K_s^l - 1}{2\varphi} + \frac{\varphi K_s^h + 1}{\varphi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin^2 \theta + (\varphi K_s^h + 1)$$

$$c_1 = \left(\frac{\varphi K_s^l - 1}{2\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin^2 \theta + 1$$

Then the linear relationship between the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio can be obtained by

$$v_{12} = \frac{l \cos^2 \theta \sin \theta}{\varphi K_s^h + 2} \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) E_1 - \frac{(h+h_0) K_s^h}{2l(\varphi K_s^h + 2)} \left(\frac{1}{K_f^l} - \frac{1}{K_s^l} \right) \sin \theta \quad (35)$$

$$v_{21} = \frac{l \sin \theta (\varphi K_s^l - 1)}{2K_s^l} \frac{c_0 + c_1}{c_1(\varphi K_s^h + 1) - c_0} E_2 - \frac{l \sin \theta (\varphi K_s^l - 1)}{h+h_0} \frac{\varphi K_s^h + 2}{c_1(\varphi K_s^h + 1) - c_0} \quad (36)$$

$$v_{23} = \frac{\varphi - 1/K_s^l}{4\varphi} \left(\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_f^l} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_s^l} \right) \frac{(c_0 - c_1)(h+h_0)}{c_1(\varphi K_s^h + 1) - c_0} E_2 - \frac{\varphi K_s^l - 1}{2\varphi} \left(\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_f^l} - \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{K_s^l} \right) \frac{\varphi K_s^h}{c_1(\varphi K_s^h + 1) - c_0} \quad (37)$$

Fig. 9. Analytical and FE simulations of Poisson's ratio v as a function of Young's modulus (a) E_1 / E_s and (b) E_2 / E_s of the 3D new design carried for $\alpha = 2$, $\theta = 30^\circ$, $\beta = 0.1$ (scatters and the line with symbols corresponding to the FE and analytical simulations respectively).

4.5 Relative Density and The Modulus

According to Gibson's theory, the modulus of an open-cell structure could be expressed as [15]

$$\frac{E}{E_s} = k \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_s} \right)^n = k \rho_r^n \quad (38)$$

where, ρ_s is the density of the solid bulk material and ρ_r is the relative density of the cellular structure. k is a structure specific constant that describes the sensitivity of the modulus to changes in relative density. For regular stochastic open-cell cellular structure $k = 1$.

The modulus of 3D re-entrant cellular structure with strut cross sectional dimension t being much smaller than h and l is expressed as [14,16]

$$E^{\text{Re}} / E_s = k^{\text{Re}} \rho_r^2 \quad (39)$$

where, k^{Re} is related to the length of struts h and l and the re-entrant angle θ . As we have supposed that both the adding struts h_0 and the original struts h have an cross section thickness t . Then the relative density of the 3D new structure could be written as

$$\rho_r = \frac{(h + h_0)bt + 2(l - t / \cos \theta)bt}{(h + h_0)l^2 \cos^2 \theta} \quad (40)$$

From Eq. (41) and (42) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_1}{E_s} &\propto (\lambda + \rho_r)\rho_r \\ \frac{E_2}{E_s} &\propto (\lambda + \rho_r)\rho_r \\ \text{i. e. } \frac{E}{E_s} &\propto \lambda\rho_r + \rho_r^2 \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

It is obvious that the elastic properties of the proposed 3D new structure is depend on the force constant ratio λ and the relative density ρ_r . Eq. (41) also shows the main mechanism of the enhancement of the adding ribs re-entrant structure.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, inspired by the 2D adding ribs re-entrant structure [12] and 3D re-entrant cellular structure [9,16], a 3D adding ribs re-entrant cellular structure is proposed. Elastic properties of the 3D new structure is given by analytical and FE simulations. Compare with the 3D re-entrant cellular structure, the 3D new design has a great enhancement on the Young's modulus especially in direction 1. Changing the adding rib's force constant only, an evident linear relationship between Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio is found both analytical and FE simulations. Different from the 2D structure, we also proved that the Poisson's ratio ν_{23} is negative for all $\lambda > 0$ and $t < l$. This is also important for this structure is a great choice for materials with negative Poisson's ratio in one direction and zero or positive Poisson's ratio in other two directions. We also shown the main mechanism of the enhancement of the 3D adding ribs re-entrant cellular structure based on the relationship between the modulus and the relative density of the 3D new design.

It should be noted the enhancement concept of adding ribs can also be introduced to other periodic auxetic structures which is under studying.

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